

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist – The nexus of health and labour exploitation among migrant populations in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye: a scoping review

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TITLE			
Title	1	The nexus of health and labour exploitation among migrant populations in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye: a scoping review	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	<p>Introduction Labour exploitation is a social determinant of health, acting as both a risk factor for poor health outcomes and a barrier to accessing healthcare. This scoping review aims to identify the health outcomes of migrant victims of labour exploitation and the barriers they face in accessing healthcare in the Eastern Mediterranean Region and Türkiye. It also seeks to identify gaps in evidence for future studies.</p> <p>Inclusion criteria Studies conducted with/among migrants in the Eastern Mediterranean Region and Türkiye who</p>	2

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		<p>experience labour exploitation and related health issues or barriers to accessing healthcare, regardless of age, nationality, gender, ethnicity, or migration status.</p> <p>Methods This review follows the updated Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) guidelines for designing scoping reviews. We will include English and Arabic language peer-reviewed publications and grey literature between March 2011 until present. Using a three-phase search strategy, an initial limited search in PubMed and Google Scholar was undertaken to refine the keywords. A full search of all selected databases and screening of references of previously published reviews will be conducted to ensure the inclusion of relevant articles unaccounted for in our full search. We will search Cochrane, PubMed, Web of Science, SCOPUS databases and, Google Scholar and Overton for grey literature. Using COVIDENCE, two independent reviewers will screen the titles, abstracts and full texts for eligibility and inclusion. Relevant information will be extracted using a tailored extraction data sheet.</p> <p>Analysis Extracted data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics and an inductive content analysis approach. This review employs an intersectional framework, as well as a structural, symbolic, and interpersonal violence framework, alongside Tanahashi's health service coverage framework to analyse and synthesise the data.</p> <p>Results This review will illustrate the key themes and relationships between labour exploitation, health outcomes, access to healthcare aspects, and influencing factors using appropriate summaries and visual tools. A comprehensive populated labour exploitation continuum framework incorporating practised forms identified in the literature will be developed within which associations to health outcomes and access to healthcare aspects will be drawn.</p> <p>Dissemination This work will be disseminated through publication in a peer-reviewed journal and presentation in relevant forums.</p>	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	<p>Labour exploitation serves as a risk factor for poor health outcomes and a barrier to healthcare access among migrants. This phenomenon is complex, particularly due to its implicit nature, as it often goes unrecognised by law enforcement despite its impact on victims' mental and physical health. In the Eastern Mediterranean region and Turkey, labour exploitation is evident, exacerbated by existing migration regulatory systems in some parts of the region that grant employers disproportionate power over their migrant employees. This leaves migrant workers</p>	3,4,5

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		<p>vulnerable to exploitation and abuse while restricting their access to healthcare and sociolegal protections.</p> <p>Despite increasing attention to labour exploitation, the current landscape reveals a gap, with policies and research primarily focusing on its most severe forms, i.e. forced labour and modern slavery, predominantly framing the issue through a criminal lens. Consequently, milder and routine forms of labour exploitation remain largely unaddressed in policy discourse and academic literature. This lack of clear recognition of labour exploitation in existing laws and protection policies further diminishes its visibility.</p> <p>To date, studies on labour exploitation in relation to health have predominantly examined its severe forms, including modern slavery, forced labour, and trafficking for sexual exploitation. However, a thorough examination of exploitative practices and milder or routine forms of exploitation and their implications for migrants' access to healthcare and overall health outcomes has received little consideration. Furthermore, research on labour exploitation and migrants' health in the Eastern Mediterranean region remains scarce.</p> <p>This review aims to capture a range of sources to map the scope and nature of the most relevant topical literature on the nexus of labour exploitation and health in migrant populations in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye. We will summarise key themes in this body of knowledge, pinpoint major substantive areas where further evidence generation is required, and disentangle the health-related aspects of labour exploitation in migrant populations.</p>	
Objectives	4	<p>Our objectives are to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Identify the direct and indirect consequences of labour exploitation on migrants' physical and psychosocial health in the Eastern Mediterranean Region and Türkiye. b. Identify the existing barriers and challenges in accessing healthcare and support services for migrant victims of labour exploitation in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye. c. Map the existing systems, policy interventions, and promising practices addressing the health of migrant victims of labour exploitation in the Eastern Mediterranean Region and Türkiye. 	7
METHODS			

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Protocol and registration	5	The scoping review protocol will be registered on F1000 research, and all relevant project documents will be registered on Zenodo.	9
Eligibility criteria	6	<p>Scope: Studies referring to migrants residing in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye who experience any form of labour exploitation along the continuum of decent work and forced labour and experience associated health issues or barriers to accessing healthcare due to their labour exploitation experience.</p> <p>Context: The World Health Organisation-designated Eastern Mediterranean Region and Türkiye.</p> <p>This region is an ideal model for studying labour exploitation and health due to its diverse migrant population, varying migration patterns, and health systems development. While there are evident cases of labour exploitation, the impact on migrants' health is not well understood. These factors make the region suitable for exploring the relationship between labour exploitation and health. Our operational and research experience in the area provides valuable insights for our study.</p> <p>Timeframe: This review will examine articles published after March 2011, coinciding with the Syrian revolution and extending to the present, including the 2016 EU-Türkiye deal. This timeframe highlights two key developments: the Syrian civil war, resulting in over 14 million displaced individuals and heightened vulnerability to exploitation in host countries, and the EU-Türkiye deal, which externalises migration issues by restricting migrants' entry into Europe. This deal allows governments to contain migrants, exploiting their vulnerabilities for cheap labor and increasing their risk of exploitation.</p> <p>Document type: Both peer-reviewed articles and grey literature will be included to capture as much as possible the full breadth of existing knowledge on this topic.</p> <p>Languages: The review will be limited to full articles published in English or Arabic or available in English or Arabic translation, as these are the languages covered by the members of this team.</p>	
Information sources*	7	<p>Timeframe: March 2011 until present. Date of most recent search: 24/02/2025</p> <p>A literature search will be conducted using the following databases: - Cochrane https://www.cochranelibrary.com/central/about-central</p>	9

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PubMed https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ - Web of Science www.webofscience.com - SCOPUS https://www.scopus.com/home.uri - Institute of Tropical Medicine (ITM) library's discovery service https://research.ebsco.com - For grey literature, including relevant policy documents, we will use Google Scholar https://scholar.google.com/ and Overton https://www.overton.io/ as a secondary source, and we will take the 200 first results of each, as recommended by Haddaway et al., 2015. - Reports published on websites of international organisations such as the International Labor Organization, UNICEF, World Bank, UN Women, and Save the Children. 	
Search	8	<p>PubMed search</p> <p>Publication date: 03/2011 until the present Search date: 24/02/2025 Results: 154,312</p> <p>Search syntax: "Transients and Migrants"[Mesh] OR "Refugees"[Mesh] OR "Emigrants and Immigrants"[Mesh] OR "Undocumented Immigrants"[Mesh] OR "Refugee Camps"[Mesh] OR "Emigration and Immigration"[Mesh] OR "non-citizen" OR "non citizen" OR "non-native" OR "non-native" OR "foreign" OR "resident" OR "asylum seeker" OR "migrant" OR "immigrant" OR "unaccompanied minor" OR "unaccompanied migrant" OR "undocumented" OR "illegal" OR "irregular" OR "allochthonous" OR "third country nationals" OR "labor migra*" OR "labour migra*" OR "immigrant work*" OR "economic migra*" OR "economic immigra*" OR "migratory status" "labor exploit*" OR "labour exploit*" OR "exploitative practic*" OR "exploitation" OR "exploitative labor" OR "exploitative labour" OR "Human Traffick*" OR "trafficking in human beings" OR "Sex trafficking" OR "Labor traffick*" OR "Labour traffick*" OR "child trafficking" OR "trafficked" OR "Forced labor" OR "forced labour" OR "Coerced labor" OR "coerced labour" OR "Child labor" OR "child labour" OR "Indentured servitude" OR "Debt bondage" OR "Domestic servitude" OR "domestic work" OR "Modern slavery" OR "Manual low-skilled jobs" OR "low skilled" OR "low-skilled" OR "Workplace hazard" OR "hazardous work" OR "Dehumanization" OR "Coercion" OR "Accidents, Occupational"[Mesh] OR "Working Condition" OR "Occupational Exposure" OR "Workplace Violence" OR "Precarious employment" OR "Seasonal worker" OR "low wages" OR "underpayment" OR "labor" OR "labour" OR "adverse working condition" OR "Poor working condition" OR "Adverse work experiences" OR "farm*" OR "agriculture" OR "fishing" OR "cheap labor" OR "cheap</p>	

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		<p>labour” OR “occupation” OR “work” OR “employ*” OR "Farmers"[Mesh] OR "Mining"[Mesh] OR "Construction Industry"[Mesh] OR "Sex Work"[Mesh] OR "Textile Industry"[Mesh] OR “plantation” OR “forestr*” OR “abuse at work” OR “harassment at work” OR “work-related illness” OR “informal labor” OR “informal labour” OR “gig work” OR “daily wage labor” OR “daily wage labour” OR “logging industry” OR “timber industry”</p> <p>"Health"[Mesh] OR "Health Services Accessibility"[Mesh] OR “Access health” OR "Access to Primary Care"[Mesh] OR “Healthcare access” OR “Healthcare visit” OR “Health facillit*” OR “health cent*” OR “primary care” OR “secondary care” OR “tertiary care” OR “mental health servic*” OR “psychosocial” OR “psychological support” OR “psychosocial support” OR “mental health support” OR “psychiatric care” OR “social support” OR “social work” OR “hazard” OR “injur*” OR “risk*” OR “wellbeing” OR “well-being” OR “sick” OR “ill” OR “Occupational health”</p> <p>(Afghanistan[MeSH Terms]) OR (Bahrain[MeSH Terms]) OR (Djibouti[MeSH Terms]) OR (Egypt[MeSH Terms]) OR (Iran[MeSH Terms]) OR (Iraq[MeSH Terms]) OR (Jordan[MeSH Terms]) OR (Kuwait[MeSH Terms]) OR (Lebanon[MeSH Terms]) OR (Libya[MeSH Terms]) OR (Morocco[MeSH Terms]) OR (Oman[MeSH Terms]) OR (Pakistan[MeSH Terms]) OR (Qatar[MeSH Terms]) OR (Saudi Arabia[MeSH Terms]) OR (Somalia[MeSH Terms]) OR (Sudan[MeSH Terms]) OR (Syria[MeSH Terms]) OR (Tunisia[MeSH Terms]) OR (United Arab Emirates[MeSH Terms]) OR (Yemen[MeSH Terms]) OR (Türkiye[MeSH Terms]) OR (Turkey[MeSH Terms]) OR "Middle East"[Mesh] OR "Africa, Northern"[Mesh] OR "Arab World"[Mesh] OR “North Africa” OR “Arab region” OR “Eastern Mediterranean region” OR “Greater Middle East” OR “Middle East and North Africa” OR “Middle East and Northern Africa” OR “MENA”</p>	
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	<p>All identified references through the search strategy will be gathered and imported into Zotero, and duplicate entries will be eliminated. Following a preliminary test, three separate reviewers will examine titles and abstracts to determine if they meet the review’s inclusion criteria. The review will document the reasons for excluding titles and abstracts during this screening process. Any disagreements between reviewers at any stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion or by consulting a third reviewer. Sources deemed potentially relevant will be obtained in full, and their citation information will be entered into COVIDENCE. Three independent reviewers will thoroughly assess the full text of selected citations against the inclusion criteria. The scoping review will document and report the reasons for excluding any full-text sources that don't meet these criteria. Any discrepancies between reviewers during this process will be settled through discussion or with the help of a third reviewer. The final scoping review will provide a</p>	10

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		comprehensive report of the search results and study inclusion process, including a PRISMA flow diagram for visual representation.	
Data charting process‡	10	<p>Two independent reviewers will extract data from the selected papers using a custom-designed data extraction tool. This tool will capture specific information about participants, concepts, context, study methods, and key findings relevant to the review questions. The tool was designed after a preliminary search of relevant literature on labour exploitation in migrant populations.</p> <p>The initial data extraction tool will be piloted, modified, and refined iteratively as necessary during the title and abstract screening process. Further adjustments may be made while extracting data from full-text sources. All modifications will be documented in the scoping review. Any disagreements between reviewers will be resolved through discussion or by consulting additional reviewers. If needed, the reviewers may contact study authors to request missing or additional data.</p>	10,11
Data items	11	<p>The main variables include:</p> <p>a. Study/document characteristics: Author(s), Affiliations, Title of paper, Year of publication, Origin/country of origin (where the source was published or conducted), Document type, Study population source, Sample size, Methodology/methods.</p> <p>b. Participants characteristics: Age group, sexuality, Gender identity, Race and/or ethnicity, Country of origin, Host country, Migratory status, Employment status, Language, relevant sociocultural factors</p> <p>c. Concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labour exploitation perpetrator, typology, characteristics, industry or sector involved • Mental, physical and social health outcomes. • Access to healthcare dimensions using the evidence synthesis framework of the WHO’s Handbook for conducting assessments of barriers to effective coverage with health services. • Identified coping strategies and promising practices. <p>d. Context includes the country and the setting where the study is conducted.</p>	11
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	

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		<p>Since our objectives are to map existing evidence and identify gaps, no critical appraisal is foreseen for this review.</p>	
<p>Synthesis of results</p>	<p>13</p>	<p>Quantitative Analysis: A descriptive analysis will summarize the included studies, focusing on the number of studies by country, study designs, publication years, sample sizes, and demographic characteristics of migrant populations.</p> <p>Qualitative Analysis: An inductive content analysis will synthesize qualitative data, exploring themes such as forms of labour exploitation, associated health outcomes, and barriers to healthcare access. Special attention will be given to vulnerabilized populations at higher risk of exploitation, including children, older adults, racial and ethnic minorities, gender and sexual minorities, marginalized subgroups, those with lower education levels, individuals with disabilities, and informal workers.</p> <p>Mapping of Evidence: The analysis will identify research gaps and areas of concentration, including geographical study distribution, frequently studied employment sectors, underrepresented migrant groups, understudied health outcomes, healthcare access types, and recommendations for future research and policy implications.</p> <p>The scoping review results will be presented using structured narratives and visuals (tables, maps, figures) with software like Power BI. A narrative summary will highlight key themes, the current state of research, major findings on labour exploitation and health impacts, and identify trends, patterns, and literature gaps. A populated labour exploitation continuum framework will be developed to link identified practices with health outcomes and access to healthcare.</p> <p>A dedicated section will address research gaps, promising practices, future research directions, and implications for policy.</p> <p>Visual aids will include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram**: Study selection process. 2. Tables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Characteristics of included studies - Summary of key findings by theme - Overview of health outcomes related to labour exploitation 3. Figures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bar chart by country distribution - Population characteristics chart - Pie chart of study designs - Interactive heat map of research concentration by sector. 4. Conceptual Frameworks: 	<p>11,12</p>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A diagram of relationships between exploitation, health outcomes, and influencing factors. - A populated labour exploitation continuum framework with associations to health outcomes and access to healthcare aspects. 5. Word Cloud: Frequently mentioned terms related to health impacts and exploitation forms.	
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
Characteristics of sources of evidence:	15	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
Synthesis of results	18	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
Limitations	20	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
Conclusions	21	This will be determined after the review is completed.	
FUNDING			
Funding	22	The authors declared that no grants were involved in supporting this work.	

JBI = Joanna Briggs Institute; PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.

* Where *sources of evidence* (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley (6) and Levac and colleagues (7) and the JBI guidance (4, 5) refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).